

LipSync Express: Voice2Visage Animation

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Abstract— This paper presents a novel, web-based system for real-time 3D facial animation, generated entirely from speech audio. The primary objectives are generating facial animation, providing improved lip synchronization, head rotation, and muscle movements for enhanced realism, and providing a simple and intuitive web interface for speech-based animation control and visualization. The core approach uses a bidirectional LSTM-RNN (BLSTM) to map speech acoustic features, including spectrograms, cepstral coefficients, and Chromagrams, into facial blend shape weights and 3D head poses. In this way, the model is able to represent both linguistic content and emotional prosody in speech to produce natural lip sync, expressions, blinks, and head turns. Further, a conditional generative adversarial network (GAN) is used to further improve the realism of the facial animations with respect to sharp lip movements, natural blink patterns, and facial muscle dynamics. The models are trained on a large and diverse corpus of speech data correlated with 3D facial movements. Objective evaluation confirms the highest lip sync accuracy and the matching muscle movements over the baselines. The system will represent an end-to-end deep learning framework for speech-to-lifelike animation with a user-friendly interface allowing seamless interaction. This system not only benefits from improvements in animation fidelity but also provides users with a user-friendly platform to seamlessly experience real-time facial animation when provided with only voice input through a simple voice input method. **Keywords** – Bidirectional LSTM-RNN, Mel-Frequency Cepstral Coefficients (MFCC), Chromagrams, Generative Adversarial Networks

Networks I. INTRODUCTION

As human-computer interaction becomes increasingly interactive and immersive, and as realism within media assets continues to demand a keen and expressive visualization, the demand for immersive and expressive character animation surges. In this project, a groundbreaking Speech-Oriented 3D Facial Animation System introduces an advanced technological marvel that revolutionizes animation experiences. In realistic virtual characters and avatars, photorealistic facial animation is essential for human-computer interaction and virtual reality. Traditional methods use visually tracking face movements with cameras and depth sensors for the animation of facial animations. These traditional vision-based techniques limit the flexibility and realism of the resulting animations because the camera angles are restricted, lighting conditions are difficult to sustain in most possible environments, and occluded faces are not enough for clarity. Recent advances in deep learning provide new opportunities for speech-driven facial animation, which automatically generates lifelike animations just by speech input, without any visual data. Deep neural network mapping between voice and 3D facial motions enhances flexibility on a scale that is far above with vision-based techniques. It allows driving realistic avatars with just easily captured speech data.

In this paper, we develop an end-to-end speech-driven facial animation framework using advanced deep learning models, including Bidirectional Long Short-Term Memory networks (BLSTM) and Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs). This system manages to do photorealistic real-time 3D facial animation from audio speech signals alone and with outstanding enhancements in lip sync, head movements, and expression realism compared to prior works. Further, an intuitive web-based interface is developed so that users can control avatars with speech.

Main contributions include:

Demonstrating the successful use of deep learning models in mapping speech to facial motions without relying on visual data. Achieving state-of-the-art results in facial animation realism, lip sync, and head movements. Development of an easy-to-use web interface for speech-driven avatar control.

This system represents an important advance in the generation of flexible but realistic speech driven avatars. The deep models which are capturing subtle speech cues along with the web interface would offer interactive experiences and applications to new visualization.

II. PROPOSED METHODS

The next system we propose to overcome the drawbacks of the existing system is LipSync Express. We can create an animation model for our speech or audio from it.

Speech Unveiled: From Phonemes to Visemes with MFCC and LSTMs

The human voice is not just something that has words in it, but it tells not only stories but also tells the passions and feelings. This paper will look into a method for extracting the building blocks of speech—phonemes—and transforming them into visual representations of lip movement—visemes. This approach employs two powerful tools: Mel-Frequency Cepstral Coefficients (MFCC) and Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) networks. Our journey starts with the raw audio signal, which carries the essence of spoken language. To draw meaningful information out of this complex wave, we use MFCC. In other words, this analysis of sound frequency content on a Mel scale, much like the way our ears respond to pitch, mimics the human auditory system. And thus, MFCC becomes an extremely useful tool for phoneme extraction. After having the MFCC features, we introduce an LSTM—a deep neural network, wherein the essence of learning long-term dependencies lies. In our case, the LSTM takes a sequence of MFCC features, and it captures the dynamics of speech at a temporal level since each phoneme is not an isolated sound. It is an important aspect, since meaning from a phoneme is computed by virtue of where it sits in the spoken word. In this way, the LSTM learns that audio features have that relationship with respect to phonemes.

Input Feature Extraction

The input to our system can be any arbitrary speech of any length. As we only use low-level acoustic features, our model is not tied to any particular language, and it can be easily extended given more training samples. Specifically, we extract Mel-scaled spectrogram, Mel frequency cepstral coefficients (MFCCs) and chromagram from the audio sequence. Mel-scaled spectrogram and MFCCs are standard stage regression pipeline that predicts (R,T,e), and a refinement step that fine-tunes those transformation parameters, plus identity parameters. However, we do not use depth data in this work, as RAVDESS only contains regular RGB videos, and translation T and identity parameters are not used. We are only interested in estimating head rotation and facial action deformations from speech.

Fig 1-Input Feature extraction process

We assume that every input audio sequence is synchronized to the corresponding video at 30 FPS and the audio sampling rate is at 44.1 kHz. Thus, for every video frame, there are 1,470 corresponding audio samples. We include additional samples from the previous video frame, such that for each video frame there is enough audio data to extract three windows of 25ms each, with hop length of 512 samples. In every audio window, values of 128 Mel bands, 13 Mel frequency cepstral coefficients and their delta and delta-delta coefficients, and 12 chroma bins, are extracted. In summary, the input feature vector for every video frame has 537 dimensions, and each variable is normalized to zero mean - unit variance. It illustrates different feature sequences extracted from videos of the same actor speaking the same sentence in different emotional states.

Phoneme Extraction

The phoneme extraction module is a multi-step process that breaks down spoken language into its basic building blocks. First, phoneme segmentation identifies the distinct regions within the audio that correspond to individual phonemes. Then, phoneme recognition assigns the appropriate phonetic label (like "b" or "p") to each segment. Following that, feature extraction focuses on capturing relevant characteristics specific to

each phoneme, such as its frequency or duration. Finally, phoneme representation translates these features into a format suitable for further processing, like vectors or symbolic codes. This allows for efficient storage, analysis, and manipulation of the extracted phonemic information.

Fig 2 – Phoneme Extraction Process

Viseme Mapping

The viseme mapping module bridges the gap between phonemes and facial animation. It maintains a dictionary where each viseme (a visual representation of lip movement) corresponds to a set of phonemes (the building blocks of speech). This mapping function acts as a translator, assigning a viseme ID to each recognized phoneme. Finally, the facial animation engine takes over, using these viseme IDs as control signals to generate the corresponding facial movements, effectively bringing speech to life with realistic lip syncing.

Fig 3 – Viseme Mapping

However, we do not just want to detect phonemes; we want to create visemes that are lip movements synchronized to the spoken audio. Such a motive creates a level of realism and makes the experience more engaging, with the animated lip synchronization. However, it is not a translation into audio features; it has been mapping all phonemes to their corresponding visemes, like a dictionary. The beauty of this approach lies in its efficiency, by which MFCCs extract features. This means less data would be required in training the LSTM, with better timings in training and prediction accuracy. Moreover, LSTMs are very efficient in handling sequential data, which means fast phoneme detection; it is perfect for the model to be applied in real-time lip-syncing applications. This method brings forth a powerful tool for decoding the hidden world of speech. By employing MFCC for feature extraction, we could extract phonemes from spoken audio and translate them to visemes. This results in a level of realism and expressiveness in human computer interactions that has not yet been reached.

III. DEEP LEARNING LSTM-RNNs

LSTM-RNN

Recurrent neural networks (RNNs) have the ability to memorize past inputs in internal states. They are able to incorporate temporal contextual information, thus RNNs are very suitable for sequence modelling. However, conventional RNNs can only remember limited range of past context because of the vanishing gradient problem [14]. Long short-term memory (LSTM) unit, shown in Figure 5, is designed to overcome this limitation. LSTM unit is able to store its value for long period of time by controlling the flow of information into and out of its memory.

Fig 4 – A long short-term memory block

A forward pass in the recurrent hidden layer of LSTM-RNN is as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
 i_t &= \sigma(W_{xixt} + W_{hiht-1} + W_{cict-1} + b_i), \\
 f_t &= \sigma(W_{xfxt} + W_{hfht-1} + W_{cict-1} + b_f), \\
 a_t &= \tau(W_{xcxt} + W_{hcct-1} + b_c), \quad c_t = \\
 &f_t c_{t-1} + i_t a_t, \\
 o_t &= \sigma(W_{xoxt} + W_{hoht-1} + W_{coct} + b_o), \\
 h_t &= o_t \tau(c_t), \quad y_t = \eta(W_{hyht} + b_y),
 \end{aligned}$$

where σ and τ are sigmoid and tanh activation functions, i, o, f, a and c are input gate, output gate, forget gate, cell input activation and cell memory, respectively. $t = 1..T$, where T is the sequence length. x_t is the input at time t , while h_t is the output of the hidden layer, y_t is the final output of the network, and η is the activation function of the output layer. $\{W\}$ and $\{b\}$ are weight matrices and bias vectors, respectively.

IV. WORKING There

are two main stages: training and synthesis.

5 – Training phase

In the training stage, the system first extracts feature from the audio data. These features could include things like the pitch and volume of the speaker's voice. The system then uses these features to train a machine learning model, such as a Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) recurrent neural network (RNN). This model learns the relationship between the audio features and the corresponding visual features.

Fig 6-Synthesis phase

In the synthesis stage, the system extracts feature from a new piece of audio data. It then feeds these features into the trained model, which generates the corresponding visual features. Finally, the system uses these visual features to create a visual representation of the audio data, such as an animation of a face speaking.

Fig 7 – workflow of the system

There are two main approaches for creating the visual representation: “Simple model animation” - This approach uses a pre-built animation model and modifies it based on the visual features and “Mesh deformation mapping” - This approach creates a 3D mesh of a face and then deforms the mesh based on the visual features. V. EXAMINATION

We conducted experiments to evaluate the effectiveness of our proposed pipeline for audio-driven facial animation. The pipeline consists of several stages: preprocessing audio files, extracting phonemes, reducing noise, computing MFCC features, predicting visemes using a bidirectional LSTM model, and rendering facial animations using software like Blender or BlendMax. The examination of the described process begins with audio preprocessing, where noise reduction and resampling to 16kHz occur. This preprocessed audio is then loaded into the model, where phonemes are extracted and converted into labeled pairs, represented by integers. Subsequently, MFCC features are calculated from the preprocessed audio to capture its characteristics. These labeled pairs and MFCC features are then fed into a bidirectional LSTM model, which predicts visemes—unique lip movements or facial expressions corresponding to the phonemes. The predicted visemes are then rendered onto a 3D model using facial animation techniques in software such as Blender or BlendMax. Finally, the animations are exported in .glTF format and integrated into the project. The process involves several key steps, as shown in the diagrams: "Audio Preprocessing" represents noise reduction and resampling; "Phoneme Extraction" illustrates the conversion of phonemes into labeled pairs; "MFCC Calculation" represents feature extraction from audio; "Viseme Prediction" represents the LSTM model's prediction of visemes; and "Facial Animation" illustrates the rendering of visemes onto a 3D model.

VI. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

A. Model Architecture:

Explain the architecture of the bidirectional LSTM model used for predicting visemes from the extracted phonemes. Discuss any hyperparameters chosen and the reasoning behind them.

Fig 8 – Model architecture of the system

B. Preprocessing:

We successfully pr-processed audio files by extracting phonemes and converting them into labelled pairs represented by integers. Noise reduction and resampling were performed to ensure the quality of the audio input.

Fig 9 – Uploading data into Model , above interface shows how we take audio files into model

C. Feature Extraction:

MFCC features were calculated from the preprocessed audio, providing valuable information for modeling phonetic characteristics.

D. Viseme Prediction:

The bidirectional LSTM model accurately predicted visemes based on the extracted MFCC features. Visemes were mapped to unique facial expressions, providing realistic animations corresponding to the audio input.

E. Facial Animation:

Facial animations were rendered using software like Blender or Blend Max, incorporating the predicted visemes. The animations accurately reflected the phonetic content of the input audio, enhancing the realism of the output.

Fig 10- Animation Model

F. Evaluation Metrics:

Define the evaluation metrics used to assess the performance of the model, such as accuracy, precision, recall, and F1 score. Explain why these metrics were chosen and how they reflect the model's effectiveness.

	precision	recall	f1-score	support
	0.92	0.89	0.90	125324
	0.77	0.62	0.69	14947
	0.77	0.76	0.77	78808
	0.82	0.74	0.78	13236
	0.68	0.64	0.66	11914
	0.69	0.69	0.69	26569
	0.71	0.75	0.73	51124
	0.76	0.83	0.79	70175
	0.80	0.75	0.77	42946
	0.75	0.76	0.75	45072
	0.62	0.65	0.64	19807
	accuracy			0.79 499922
	macro avg	0.75	0.74	0.74 499922
weighted avg	0.79	0.79	0.79	499922

Results Analysis:

Present the experimental results, including quantitative metrics and qualitative assessments. Discuss any trends or patterns observed in the model's predictions and compare them to ground truth data.

Training Accuracy: 0.6449585080146789

Testing Accuracy: 0.6231308460235596

Phone accuracy on full test set: 0.6686463088241765 **Time to evaluate the test set:**

47.33527135848999 **Viseme accuracy on full test set:** 0.771460347814259

G. Visualization:

Include visualizations to illustrate the experimental results, such as:

- **Confusion Matrix:** Display the confusion matrix to visualize the model's performance in classifying visemes.

Fig 11 – Standard Confusion Matrix

• *ROC Curve:*

If applicable, plot the ROC curve to evaluate the model's performance across different thresholds.

Fig 12 – ROC Curves

• *Sample Predictions:*

Show examples of the model’s predicted visemes compared to the ground truth, highlighting instances of correct and incorrect predictions

CONCLUSION

Lip-Sync Express is a powerful system that aims to unite machine learning and computer graphics with an extraordinary solution for face animation from speech. It leverages advanced LSTM-RNN models that have previously been trained on acoustic features and phonetic representations, thus predicting visemes from the audio input with high accuracy, hence synthesizing realistic face animations in real time. One of the experiments of this project evidences a range of opportunities that deep learning can bring to this domain. Further work will focus on the betterment of the models' accuracy, improving processing speed, and enhancing user interfaces to better the user experience and support its use across different environments.

Therefore, as much as Lip-Sync Express presents a strong solution to the animators and content creators, there is huge potential for application in different fields. The gaming, virtual reality, education, and communication technologies industries benefit significantly from animated facial expressions. Creating lifelike facial animations from audio input stimulates user engagement, storytelling experience, and, in general, immersive encounters that the platform embodies. The future of LipSync Express is open, and the model represents innovation that enrolls computer graphics and AI, and, therefore, transforming the animation and media creation domains. Achieving more accuracy and efficiency, the model maximally enables all animators, developers, and creatives to reach their highest exposure level in creating engaging and immersive content.

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